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HAURICoPSS: Home Automation Using Radio Frequency Identification Controlled Power Switch System

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Master Teacher I

Abstract—This paper presents the design, development, and performance evaluation of the *Home Automation Using Radio Frequency Identification Controlled Power Switch System* (HAURICoPSS), aimed at enhancing household energy efficiency, operational safety, and convenience. The proposed system integrates an RFID RC522 reader, Arduino Uno microcontroller, relay modules, LEDs, buzzer, and a 16×2 LCD display to enable contactless control of household electrical power via RFID key cards. A prototype was constructed in a miniature house model, with all components interconnected through custom-programmed circuitry. Experimental testing assessed the device's detection sensitivity and switching efficiency. Results indicated an average RFID detection time of 1.3 seconds and a 100% success rate in both power activation and deactivation across multiple trials. The system also incorporates a buzzer alert for unauthorized card access and provides real-time power status feedback on the LCD. The findings demonstrate that HAURICoPSS offers a cost-effective, reliable, and user-friendly solution for reducing standby power consumption and improving security in residential and commercial environments.

Keywords—RFID, home automation, Arduino Uno, power switch, energy efficiency, smart home technology.

Objective:

This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate the *Home Automation Using Radio Frequency Identification Controlled Power Switch System* (HAURICoPSS) to promote energy conservation, enhance safety, and improve convenience in household power management.

Rationale:

The rising demand and cost of electricity in the Philippines, alongside the country's reliance on thermal power plants, make power saving and management essential. Many households waste energy by leaving appliances on when not in use, contributing to the depletion of natural resources. Given the country's high temperature, air conditioners are often left running unnecessarily, further increasing power consumption. Technological advancements now offer practical solutions to address this issue. Among these, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology provides an efficient and automated way to control power usage—activating appliances only when needed and cutting power when not in use. Widely used in hotels and other facilities, RFID-based systems can be applied to households and establishments to promote energy conservation, reduce costs, and improve convenience and security.

Methods:

The system employed an RFID RC522 module, Arduino Uno microcontroller, relay modules, LEDs, buzzer, and 16×2 LCD display to control electrical power via RFID key cards. A miniature house

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prototype was constructed, integrating all components through programmed circuitry. Testing involved measuring RFID detection time and evaluating the efficiency of switching operations.

Results:

The device detected authorized RFID cards within 1.3 seconds and achieved 100% efficiency in both power activation and deactivation across multiple trials. Unauthorized card use triggered an audible buzzer alarm. The LCD provided real-time status updates ("Room Power is On/Off").

Conclusion:

HAURICoPSS demonstrated a reliable, low-cost, and user-friendly solution for household automation, effectively reducing standby power wastage while enhancing security. Its contactless operation offers practical applications in residential, commercial, and institutional settings. Future enhancements may integrate biometric authentication and AI-based automation for improved personalization and functionality.

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